

Financial Ratios as a predictor of Industrial health: A study in Assam Cooperative Jute Mill.

Sampurna Khound

Assistant professor

Department of Economics

Darrang College, Tezpur

Abstract:

Throughout the years, huge number of businesses have succeeded while some others are struggle for survival and subsequently failed. There is a considerable literature concerned with the failure of the industries. Much of this failure literature developed in 1980s and 1990s and focus on affecting heavy industries. Industrial failure is a common problem in both developed and developing countries. Financial ratios have played an important part in evaluating the performance and financial condition of any industrial unit. Over the years empirical studies repeatedly have demonstrated the usefulness of financial ratios. Financially distresses industrial unit can be separate from non-failure units in the year before the declaration of bankruptcy at an accurate rate by examining financial ratios. The motivation to undertake this study was provided the failure of industrial units in Assam over the last decades. In this study an attempt has been made to evaluate the financial condition of Assam Cooperative Jute Mill.

Key Words: Financial Ratios, Industrial Health, Financially Distress, Industrial Sickness.

Introduction:

Industrial sickness is a universal problem and many scholars from India and foreign have made attempt to identify the symptoms and causes of sickness. Increasing incidence of sickness has been a matter of great concern for government, society in general and management of banking and financial institutions in particular. Industry faced the problem of industrial sickness resulted in partial and total closure of the industrial units. Industrial sickness has implications like aggravating the serious problem of unemployment, impeding the use of available installed capacity and also has socio-economic consequences. The varied researchers are interested in assessing the financial viability of companies which have been in existence which is usually judge from the profitability, liquidity and solvency positions of companies. These aspects are represented by profit or loss, net working capital and net worth respectively. Ratios are considered as the best tool to find out the historical performance and current financial conditions of the firm and to interpret the strengths and weakness of a firm. Ratio tells about the numerical and quantitative relationship between two terms and variables. The related information can be made comparable if these ratios used in a proper and significant way. Analyst on the basis of financial operations can draw conclusions with the help of these financial ratios by using them properly. These ratios can be used as a tool for analysing financial health of the industries which involves comparison, evaluation and conclusion.

Financial ratios are widely use as predictor of failure. Failure is defined as the inability of a firm to pay its financial obligations as they mature (Beaver, 1966). A firm is considered as failure when the following events have occurred: bankruptcy, bond default, nonpayment of a preferred stock dividend, or an overdrawn bank account. It is not that the financial ratios are the predictor of failure but financial ratios are the predictor of important events and one of which is failure of the firm.

Patrick (1932) conducted a study to examine whether there was a significant difference in the trend of ratios for failed and non-failed firms at least three years prior to failure. He observed that ratios of failed firms were persistently different from the non-failed firms and net worth to debt and net profit to net worth ratios were found the best indicators of failure among the ratios used. Beaver (1966) was the first to focus on ability of ratio to predict failure of firms. Failure is defined as the inability of a firm to pay its financial obligations as they mature. Tamari (Tamari, 1966) for the first time used a multivariate study in which weighted composite of several ratios were used to indicate the possible failure. Altman (Altman, 1968) developed a predictive model using Multiple Discriminate Analysis (MDA), which is used to discriminate bankrupt firms from non-bankrupt firms on the basis of financial ratio. In India few studies have been carried out to predict industrial sickness. Kaveri (1980) used multiple discriminant analysis technique and applied to assign units in the sample to one of the groups viz. good, irregular and sick. Accuracy of prediction was found to be 76 percent in the initial sample and 69 per cent in the hold out sample for one year before event. Rao and Sarmah (1976) also applied multiple discriminant analysis to a sample of 60 textile firms comprising 30 failed and 30 non-failed firms. Gupta (1979) carried out a study using financial ratios on some homogeneous textile industry and further he tried to extend it to non-textile units as well. Srivastava (1981) applied a combination of operational, technical and financial parameters to discriminate between the sick and healthy units.

Assam is predominantly an agriculture base economy. After independence Assam has witness an unprecedented increase in population leading to heavy pressure on land, since its industrial sector besides being small has very limited employment potential. Government of India took initiatives for establishing PSE's which were considered as engine of growth. Industrialization was accelerated with the establishment of a number of resource-based industries mostly in the public sector, which were located in some of the relatively backward

areas of the state. Assam is the second largest producer of jute in India. Assam alone produces 1.6 million bales of jute. The main jute producing districts of Assam are Nagaon, Goalpara, Barpeta and Darrang district. Assam Cooperative Jute Mill (ACJM) was a major producer of jute in Assam. In 1970 the mill had started its commercial production. Though the mill has gone through financial depression due to imbalance in income and expenditure, but it has managed to grow with continuous struggle and effort. With various obstacles in production and marketing the mill has started making continuous progressive net profit from the year 1992-93. Therefore, this paper attempts to adopt a holistic approach to a better understanding of financial performance with the help of financial ratios.

Data and Methodology:

This study collected data from both primary and secondary sources. Primary data has been collected from Assam Cooperative Jute Mill with a structured questionnaire. Financial ratios were calculated from the annual report published by the mill. Secondary data has been collected from journal articles, various annual reports, books and internet as well. The study is descriptive as well as explanatory. Altman Z score model has been applied to evaluate the financial condition of Assam Co-operative Jute Mill. The scope of the study is limited to Assam Cooperative Jute Mill.

Objectives of the Study:

- To evaluate the present scenerio of Assam Cooperative Jute Mill Ltd.
- To examine the financial condition of Assam Cooperative Jute Mill Ltd.

Discussion and Analysis:

ACJM is the only jute mill in the country in co-operative society of Assam registered in the year 1959 under Assam Co-operative Society Act. The mill has been marketing its major

products i.e. gunny bags through Jute Commissioner's requisition order and the rest products such as, Hessian cloth, Multi Fold yarn, Laminated Jute Cloth etc. are sold directly to the customers of local and outside of the state. Though government has taken some measure but those are not enough for promoting the jute industry. The demand for jute products has been increasing both domestically and internationally. This increase in demand gives lots of hope and expectation to the jute industry that if these deficiencies are addressed the jute industry will progress on sustainable path also.

The mill has given stress on diversified and value-added products like-hessian cloth, M.F. Yarn and bleached, dyed and laminated hessian cloth. The commercial production of laminated hessian cloth is started from 31st March 2013 and sold in the local market. The following table shows the quality-wise production and sale turnover from 2017-18 to 2020-21.

Table: 1**The quantity-wise production and sale turnover from 2013-14 to 2020-21**

Financial Year	Production and sale	Sacking	M.F. Yarn	Hessian	Laminated Cloth	Total
2017-18	Production in MT	5508.8451	398.1430	302.3213	96.8030	6302.1128
	Sold in MT	5518.6276	377.3000	282.9982	101.4210	6280.3468
	Value in lakh	3847.99	200.96	251.51	131.87	44438.40
2018-19	Production in MT	5841.9173	4.8200	158.8548	40.1421	6045.7342
	Sold in MT	5928.4148	19.8800	170.0806	43.1498	6161.5248
	Value in Lakh	4751.16	16.57	170.78	59.54	4998.05
2019-20	Production in MT	5770.837		88.013		5858.850
	Sold in MT	5657.430		130.138		5797.568
	Value in Lakh	4706.337		247.702		4958.039
2020-21	Production in MT	3978.378		79.834		4058.212
	Sold in MT	3935.748		224.323		4160.08
	Value in lakh	4006.09		210.85		4216.98

Source: Compile from various annual reports of ACJML

From the year 2019-20 production of MF Yarn and Laminated cloth has been stopped because these two products required huge amount of raw materials but the profit margin was low. The major sales finished production of the society is done through the Jute Commission of India, Kolkata requisition order as per rate fixed by the Jute Commissioner, Kolkata and the rest are sold to the local customer.

The reasons for reduction in production and low-capacity utilization was found to be as follows:

- Capital shortage
- Very poor maintenance of machine.
- Obsolete machinery.
- Poor planning and management of production in the mill.
- Shortage of raw material
- Lack of skilled workers

Altman Z score model Test:

In 1968, An American professor Edward Altman developed this model to check financial stability and health of the firms. The study has found that this model has predicted the industrial sickness accurately. It has been proven accurately in case of selected industries that Altman Z score model gives accurate result in predicting industrial sickness. If sickness can be predicted at early stage, revival and rehabilitation becomes easier. The model has been applied to Assam Co-operative Jute Mill to evaluate the health of the industrial unit.

To calculate the Altman Z-score test we use following formula-

$$\text{Altman Z-Score} = "(1.2 \times X1) + (1.4 \times X2) + (3.3 \times X3) + (0.6 \times X4) + (1.0 \times X5)"$$

$$X1 = \text{Working Capital/ Total Assets}$$

$X2 = \text{Retained Earnings} / \text{Total Assets}$

$X3 = \text{Earnings before Interest and Tax} / \text{Total Assets}$

$X4 = \text{Market value of equity} / \text{Total Liabilities}$

$X5 = \text{Total Sales} / \text{Total Assets}$

Financial health of any company or industry is judged from the results got from various zones of the Altman Z score test.

X1 = Working Capital/ Total Assets:

“Working capital = Current Assets – Current Liabilities”

Here, company's short term financial health can be known through the company's working capital. Working Capital with positive value will indicate about the enough fund with the company to invest and grow even after meeting its short-term financial debts and obligations whereas working capital with negative value tells us about the inadequate fund and asset with the firm which tells us that the company is not in the position to invest and grow and also the company is not able to meet its short-term obligations.

“X2 = Retained Earning/Total Assets × 1.4”

This shows about the paying debt capacity of the company. If the retained earnings of the company is lower than its total asset than it is indicating that the company is borrowing funds from other sources rather than funds from its retained earnings to finance its expenditures, but if the retained earnings of the company is high than its total assets than it means that company is capable enough to finance its expenditure from its retained earnings, higher retained earnings means that company has earned enough profit over the years and have

enough funds to stay profitable and it is not in the negative position to borrow funds from outer and external sources.

“X3 = Earnings before Interest and Tax/Total Assets× 3.3”

The profit generating ability of the company solely from its operations is shown through EBIT, it measures the profitability of the company. It tells us about the revenues to be generated by the company to stay profitable and the ability of the company to fund its current and ongoing operations and clear its debt payments.

“X4 = Market value of equity/Total Liabilities × 0.6”

Market value of equity = Number of outstanding shares × Current price of stocks Market value is also known with the name of market capitalization, which tells the value of company's equity. This tells about the market value of the company, firm's low market equity value to its total liability means the poor financial strength of the firm while the high market equity value to total liabilities means good financial strength and confidence of the investors lies in the financial strength of the firm.

“X5 = Total Sales/Total Assets × 1.0”

This ratio shows about efficiency of the management of utilizing its assets to increase and generate revenues, high amount of total sales over the total assets of the company means that to generate the sales there is a need of the investment for the company which in turn will increase the company's profit whereas decreased/low total sales over the total assets means that company/management needs to use more resources and also needs to put more efforts to increase its sales which in turn will reduce the profit of the firm.

Analysis of Altman Z Score test:

It has been seen that with the help of various statistical models the industrial sickness could be predicted. “Altman Z score model” is considered to be one of the best numerical measurement predictors of sick industrial units. The following table shows the calculation and result of various financial ratios of ACJM.

Table: 2

Calculation of various ratios ACJM

Years	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Working capital/Total Assets	0.45	0.49	-0.008	-0.32	-0.26
Retained Earnings/Total Assets	0.002	0.0006	0.0009	-0.31	0.0003
EBIT/ Total Assets	0.005	0.002	0.0009	-0.31	-0.11
Market Value of Equity/ Total Liabilities	0.44	0.51	0.29	0.25	0.27
Total Sales/Total Assets	2.58	2.31	3.62	4.09	0.97

Source: Calculated from various annual reports of The Assam Co-operative Jute Mill Ltd.

Table: 3

Showing calculated value of Z score of Model Altman's

Ratios/ Year	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
X ₁	0.54	0.588	-0.0096	-0.384	-0.312
X ₂	0.0028	0.00084	0.0015	-0.434	0.00042
X ₃	0.0017	0.0066	0.0029	-1.02	-0.36

X ₄	0.26	0.31	0.17	0.15	0.16
X ₅	2.58	2.31	3.62	4.09	0.97
Z score	3.38	3.22	3.78	2.25	0.458
Zone	Safe Zone	Safe zone	Safe zone	Grey Zone	Distress zone

From the above table number 2 and table number 3 it has been clear that Altman Z score of ACJM is not very impressive as the industrial unit is in distress zone which shows that the financial situation is not good. The Altman Z score has been calculated for five years, it has been found that for 2017, 2018 and 2019 the unit is safe zone as the Z score is above 3. For the year 2020, Z score is 2.25 which is less than 2.99 and the unit is in grey zone. In the year 2021 the unit is in distress zone as the Z score has gone below 1.8.

Conclusion:

The primary objective of this paper was to analyse the financial situation of ACJM. It has been found that the mill is in financial distress situation specified by Altman Z score model. The score from the model has been a good indicator and successfully capture the prevailing condition. However, it should be noted that existence of financial distress does not always lead to the situation of bankruptcy. Adequate infrastructural facilities enhance the quantity of production and the quality of production. Availability of different infrastructure facility are of most important for expansion of the industries which are as follows- power supply, functional status of the machines, transport network and financial assistance. The NCDC (national Cooperative Development Corporation) provide an amount of Rs. 35.638 crore for a composite jute mill project through government of Assam. The project has been completed and started production, which showed a positive signal. The management of ACJM have reported that the poor production, availability of substitute in the market, lack of efficient

labour are the main reasons for the condition. Special attentions are needed to address the issues so the hindrances could be eliminated and prospects of development could be enhanced. The demand for jute products has been increasing both domestically and internationally. This increase in demand gives lots of hope and expectation to the jute industry that if these deficiencies are addressed the jute industry will progress on sustainable path also.

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